

Engineering the Photophysics of Cyanines by Chain C1' Substituents

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ABSTRACT: Cyanine dyes are widely used in bioimaging, sensing, optoelectronic, or even medicinal applications due to their tunable photophysical properties. However, controlling their electronic structures and photophysical properties remains a challenge. Here we report a novel synthetic route to pentamethine and heptamethine cyanines bearing C1' chain substituents that allow unprecedented control of their electronic and photophysical properties. By varying the terminal heterocycle (symmetric or asymmetric cyanines) and introducing various substituents at the 1'-position, such as methyl, *n*-propyl, *i*-propyl, *t*-butyl, and cyano groups, we investigated the role of symmetry breaking and its impact on bond length alternation (BLA) and out-of-plane rotation (OPR). Our analysis shows that OPR, coupled with BLA, suppresses or hypsochromically shifts the first absorption band, thereby significantly altering the absorption properties of the studied dyes. This effect is particularly pronounced in structures with different heterocyclic end groups and bulky substituents at the 1'-position, which induce strong electronic and geometric distortions. Through quantum chemical calculations and spectroscopic analyses, we demonstrate how these modifications can be utilized to fine-tune their absorption and emission properties, paving the way for their further customization. Our study not only presents the synthesis of previously unexplored novel basic cyanine derivatives but additionally offers a versatile approach to tailor their photophysics through targeted structural modifications at the 1'-position.

Introduction

Cyanines are a diverse group of organic dyes characterized by the presence of a polymethine chain connecting two heteroatoms.¹ They are classified based on the number of methine units in the chain, such as trimethine (Cy3), pentamethine (Cy5), and heptamethine (Cy7) cyanines. This distinctive conjugated system underlies their unique photophysical properties and chemical reactivity.² Notably, cyanines have demonstrated significant applications in biology and medicine.³⁻⁴ For example, Cy7 derivatives have been employed for *in vivo* fluorescent imaging because of their distinctive absorption and emission properties.⁵⁻⁶ It is possible to tune the properties of the cyanine scaffold by functionalizing the polyene chain of the dye. For example, chain-substituted cyanines have been developed for use in fluorescence microscopy,⁷ ROS (reactive oxygen species) sensing,⁸ or pH sensing,⁹ and as photoactivatable compounds.¹⁰⁻¹²

The photophysical properties of cyanine dyes, such as absorption and emission energies, fluorescence quantum yields, and solvent-dependent photophysics, are controlled by their molecular structure.¹³⁻¹⁹ The most straightforward strategy for modulating these properties is to change the number of methine units. However, more subtle design principles focus on structural modifications of

the double-bond skeleton, often achieved through functionalization.^{13, 15-16, 20-22}

Scheme 1. Schematic representation of bond length alternation (BLA) of cyanine and out-of-plane rotation (OPR).

Cyanine dyes are considered prototypical examples of nearly fully conjugated double-bond systems, where their electronic structure closely follows the particle-in-a-box model.²³ The electronic properties and transitions can be fine-tuned through Peierls distortion associated with bond length alternation (BLA, Scheme 1).²⁴⁻²⁵ This distortion was demonstrated to be caused by increasing the chain length,^{24, 26} functionalization,²² polarization by counterions,²⁷⁻²⁹ solvent polarity,³⁰ or ion pairing.^{27, 31}

Early theoretical works on hemicyanine dyes with the dimethylamino group on the end group showed that rotation around different chemical bonds, including those of the methine chain, leads to the formation of a TICT (twisted intramolecular charge transfer) state.³² Armitage, Yaron and co-workers reported in their experimental-computational study that twisting about the monomethine bridge leads to a dark state that decays nonradiatively.³³ It was also demonstrated that restraining the rotation of the CHO group in the *meso*-position of Cy5 in viscous or low-temperature media results in an increase in the fluorescence quantum yields.³⁴ On the other hand, the length of C-N bond of amino group in the even positions of the chain of cyanines has a double-bond character, its rotation is restricted,³⁵ and its presence leads to a broken symmetry, non-planar structure.³⁶ Computational studies showed that the energy barriers of the C-C bond rotations strongly depend on the choice of substituents in the *meso*-position.³⁷ We hypothesized that an important structural cyanine modification that could potentially change its electronic structure could be the forced distortion of the terminal heterocyclic rings out of the plane of the conjugated π -system, which we term out-of-plane rotation (OPR, Scheme 1) in this work. Significant electronic and structural deformations could be introduced by 1'-substituents next to the terminal heterocyclic rings, however, a reliable synthetic strategy for introducing the substituents was essentially unavailable.

The conventional approach to the synthesis of Cy5 and Cy7 derivatives involves the condensation of quaternary salts with malonaldehyde or glutacetaldehyde dianilide hydrochloride,³⁸⁻⁴² respectively (Scheme 2A). Until recently, functionalization of the polymethine chain was primarily limited to the *meso*-position, the chain central carbon atom, achieved through nucleophilic substitution⁴³ or Pd-catalyzed coupling (Scheme 2B).⁴⁴ Therefore, general methods have been developed for the preparation of chain-substituted Cy7s, utilizing ring opening of pyridinium salt derivatives⁴⁵ (Scheme 2C) and ring opening of furfural derivatives.⁴⁶ Although these methods effectively functionalize the C3', C4', and C5' positions of the polymethine chain, the possibilities for modifying the C1' position remain very limited. The 1'-substituted trimethine cyanines (Cy3) have been reported,⁴⁷ and examples of analogous 1'-substituted Cy5s are very limited.⁴⁸⁻⁴⁹ There is no general synthetic methodology for their preparation available. The synthesis of 1'-substituted Cy7 derivatives has not been reported.

Herein, we report a general approach for the functionalization of C1' as well as both C1' and C5'/C7' positions of penta-/heptamethine cyanines by condensation of 1-methyl-1*H*-2-indol-2-ylidene)but-2-enal or 6-(1-methyl-1*H*-indol-2-ylidene)hexa-2,4-dienal derivatives with either substituted 1,3,3-trimethyl-2-methyleneindoline or 3-methyl-2-methylene-2,3-dihydrobenzo[*d*]thiazole as Fisher's bases (Scheme 1D). 16 mono- and disubstituted cyanine derivatives bearing various electron-withdrawing (EWG), electron-donating (EDG), or sterically demanding 1'-substituents and the same or different heterocyclic ends have

been prepared. The developed methodology utilized short reaction times under mild conditions and simple isolation. Furthermore, we present steady-state absorption and emission spectra of all synthesized derivatives along with measurements of singlet oxygen production efficiency, photooxygenation reactivity, and photostability. Experimental photophysical properties of the synthesized cyanines were systematically correlated with the changes in the electronic structure induced by structural modifications, rationalized using quantum chemical calculations of photophysical properties. We demonstrate that substitution at the 1'-position of cyanine dyes allows an unprecedented level of control over their photophysical behavior with quantum-chemical analyses providing insight into the fundamental electronic changes.

Scheme 2. A) Conventional synthesis of Cy5 and Cy7 from malonaldehyde or glutacetaldehyde dianilide hydrochlorides. B) Strategies for the functionalization of the cyanine *meso*-position. C) Synthesis of chain substituted Cy7s via ring opening of a pyridinium salt. D) Synthesis of 1'-substituted cyanines, this work.

Results and Discussion

Controlling Photophysics by Bond Length Alternation and Out-of-Plane Rotation. We begin by considering how structural modifications affect the electronic properties of cyanine dyes, using the guidance of quantum chemistry approaches. Specifically, we focus on the impact of bond length alternation (BLA) and out-of-plane rotation (OPR, Scheme 1), and explore how these effects can be induced by substitution at the 1'-position and/or

modification of the heterocyclic end. All calculated data presented here are based on semi-empirical calculations at the IEF-PCM-ZINDO/S level of theory, assuming liquid-phase molecules optimized at the IEF-PCM-CAM-B3LYP/6-31+G** level of theory. These calculations were efficient and provided quantitative agreement with the experimental findings. Additional calculations using time-dependent density functional theory (TDDFT) results are presented in the Supporting Information. The qualitative features of the absorption spectra provided by TDDFT were analogous to those obtained by the ZINDO method, yet the calculated excitation energies were higher, which is a well described effect for cyanines.^{13, 50}

Bond length alternation, BLA (Scheme 1), is a result of an electronic phenomenon known as Peierls distortion in solid-state theory⁵¹ and has been extensively discussed in cyanine dyes.²⁴⁻²⁶ This phenomenon, which arises spontaneously in some conjugated systems, can be artificially enforced *in silico* to investigate its impact on the electronic structure.¹³ Here, we analyzed the effects of BLA by applying controlled distortions to the fully symmetric Cy7 cyanine molecule. The second structural modification, OPR (Scheme 1), describes the rotation of the terminal heterocyclic rings with respect to the plane of the conjugated π -

system, changing the relative orientation of these groups, resulting in modification of the electronic transitions.

In the planar configuration (OPR = 0°), increasing BLA resulted in an increase in the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ energy gap (Figure 1A). In addition, some spectral intensity was transferred to higher-energy transitions, particularly the $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ transition, which is consistent with expectations from the particle-in-a-box model.²³ In contrast to BLA, the out-of-plane rotation introduced more pronounced excitation energy shifts, affecting both the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ and $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transitions (Figure 1B). While the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ energy gap increased, the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ gap decreased, resulting in a bathochromic shift of the corresponding absorption bands. Therefore, OPR induced a significant redistribution of intensity between the bands. In the planar configuration, the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition is optically allowed, while the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition remains forbidden (Figure 1B). As the structure became perpendicular, $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ lost intensity and $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ became more intense. This behavior arises from a shift in the character of the molecular orbitals involved in these transitions as the localized electronic excitation changes to a charge-transfer state.²⁴ In a fully perpendicular orientation, the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition is completely forbidden, confirming the critical role of OPR in the modulation of cyanine photophysics.

Figure 1. (A) Calculated UV/vis spectra of heptamethine cyanine in the planar conformation for different degrees of BLA: non-alternated (red), moderately alternated (green: BLA = 0.02 Å), and highly alternated (blue: BLA = 0.04 Å; violet: BLA = 0.06 Å). (B) Calculated UV/vis spectra of fully symmetric Cy7 as a function of OPR of the terminal heterocyclic group. The spectra correspond to different rotational states: planar orientation (red: OPR = 0°), highly rotated (green: OPR = 70°), near-perpendicular orientation (blue: OPR = 80°), and fully perpendicular orientation (violet: OPR = 90°). (C) Calculated UV/vis spectra of fully symmetric Cy7 as a function of OPR, incorporating OPR-induced BLA through constrained optimization. The color scheme follows the same convention as that in panel B.

The combined effect of OPR and BLA revealed an even more complex relationship between structural changes and electronic properties. Because distortions of the terminal heterocycle can induce BLA, we performed partial optimizations with fixed OPR, while the other coordinates were allowed to relax (Figure 1C). The results showed that increasing OPR consistently induced BLA, leading to a distinct single-bond character between the C1' carbon and the terminal heterocycle. This structural change was accompanied by a decrease in the intensity of the first absorption band and its shift to shorter wavelengths, while the second absorption band became more intense. Up to OPR = 80°, the intensities changed only slightly. From this point

onwards, there was a rapid increase in the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ band intensity and a significant decrease in the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ band intensity, making the transition forbidden for the terminal group rotating to the perpendicular position.

The electronic origin of these intensity changes can be traced back to the nature of the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transitions. In the planar structure, the excited-state electron density remains localized on the polymethine chain. As OPR increases, the S_2 electron density progressively shifts toward the terminal heterocycle (Figure 2), transforming the transition into an optically allowed charge transfer state.

Figure 2. Natural Transition Orbitals (NTOs) characterizing the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ excitation for OPR = 0° (top) and OPR = 90° (bottom). The remaining coordinates were optimized.

With this knowledge, we hypothesized that substituents on the polymethine chain, through their electronic and steric effects, could induce both OPR and BLA effects much more effectively than could substituents at other chain positions and without the need to modify the length of the polymethine chain. Therefore, we developed the synthesis of 1'-substituted Cy7 and Cy5 and studied their physico-chemical properties together with quantum-chemical predictions.

Synthesis. Reports on the synthesis of Cy3 and Cy5 derivatives bearing a substituent at the 1'-position are rare and non-existent for Cy7. Wang and co-workers presented an elegant method for the direct functionalization of the 1'-position of Cy3 via an electrophilic substitution reaction⁴⁷ (Scheme 3A). Unfortunately, this approach is not applicable to Cy5 and Cy7, where electrophilic substitution leads to the functionalization of the *meso*-position.⁵² An interesting approach was presented by Hamer and co-workers, who described the synthesis of 1'-substituted Cy5 via the reaction of 2-ethyl-benzothiazolium salts with β -ethoxyacetaldehyde acetal⁴⁸ in pyridine (Scheme 3B).

In this work, we focused on the synthesis of Cy5/Cy7 derivatives with C1' and C5'/C7' substituents, such as methyl, *n*-propyl, *i*-propyl, *t*-butyl, and cyano groups (Table 1). Two different heterocyclic end groups, indolenine and benzothiazole moieties, were used due to their prevalent use in biological applications.¹⁰

Scheme 3. A) Synthesis of 1'-substituted Cy3 by electrophilic substitution. B) Condensation of 2-ethyl-benzothiazolium salt with β -ethoxyacetaldehyde acetal.

Table 1. The Cyanine Derivatives Used and Prepared in This Work.

Cyanine	<i>n</i>	X	R ¹	R ²	Yield /%
1	1	C(CH ₃) ₂	H	H	n.a. ^a
2	1	S	H	H	46
3	1	C(CH ₃) ₂	Me	H	49
4	1	S	<i>n</i> -Pr	H	65
5	1	C(CH ₃) ₂	<i>i</i> -Pr	H	40
6	1	S	<i>i</i> -Pr	H	55
7	1	C(CH ₃) ₂	CN	H	51
8	1	S	CN	H	90
9	1	C(CH ₃) ₂	CN	CN	91
10	2	C(CH ₃) ₂	H	H	60
11	2	S	H	H	25
12	2	C(CH ₃) ₂	Me	H	75
13	2	S	<i>n</i> -Pr	H	35
14	2	S	<i>i</i> -Pr	H	64
15	2	S	<i>t</i> -Bu	H	25
16	2	C(CH ₃) ₂	CN	H	65
17	2	C(CH ₃) ₂	CN	CN	65

^a Commercially available.

Scheme 3. A) Acid-base equilibrium of a Fischer's base. B) Synthesis of cyanines 9 and 17.

Initial attempts to prepare the 1',5'-dimethyl Cy5 (**9**) and 1',7'-dimethyl Cy7 (**17**) using commercially available dianilide hydrochloride derivatives of malonaldehyde (**18** *n* = 1) or glutaraldehyde (**19**, *n* = 2), respectively, with 2-ethylideneindolium triflate (**20**)⁵³ under basic conditions (forming Fischer's base⁵⁴, Scheme 3A) and high temperature resulted in the degradation of the starting material (Scheme 3B). Dianilide hydrochloride derivatives have already been used for the synthesis of unsubstituted Cy5 and Cy7.⁴⁰ Fortunately, the use of Fischer's base, 2-(1,3,3-trimethylindolin-

2-ylidene)acetonitrile (**21**), directly did afford the corresponding 1',7'- and 1',5'-cyano derivatives in high yields (Scheme 3B). **21** was prepared by the reaction of 1,3,3-trimethyl-2-methyleneindoline with sodium thiocyanate followed by basic hydrolysis.⁵⁵ The good thermal stability of both **21** and the dianilide hydrochloride precursor in the absence of base probably afforded this compound without significant degradation.

Scheme 4. A) Synthesis of 1'-substituted Cy5s via a vinyl chloride intermediate using 2-methylene derivatives as Fischer's bases. B) Synthesis of 1'-substituted Cy7s using quaternary salts in the presence of a base (diisopropylethylamine, DIPEA).

Then we turned our attention to indol-2-ylidene butenal **22**,⁵⁶ as a precursor for the preparation of Cy5 (Scheme 4A). Previous studies have shown that 3-dimethylaminopropenal can undergo the Vilsmeier reaction to generate reactive intermediates,⁵⁷⁻⁵⁸ which can be trapped by electron-rich moieties, such as (3-hydroxypropenyl)-1-(toluene-4-sulfonyl)-1*H*-indole-5-carbonitrile²⁹ and other indole derivatives.⁵⁹⁻⁶⁰ The conversion of enaminaldehydes to their iminium salts has been reported to give chloropentadiene iminium derivatives,^{57-58, 61} and a similar strategy was used for the synthesis of 1'-cyano Cy3.⁴⁹ Inspired by these findings, (indolin-2-ylidene)butenal **22** was converted to the corresponding vinyl chloride that subsequently gave **8** in the presence of a Fischer's base in high yield.

In general, Fischer's bases are difficult to manipulate due to their reactivity.⁶² For the preparation of monosubstituted Cy7 derivatives listed in Table 1, they were generated from the corresponding indolinium- and benzothiazolium-based quaternary salts (Scheme 3A). These salts were prepared from the corresponding 2-substituted 3,3-dimethyl-3*H*-indole or benzo[*d*]thiazole derivatives by *N*-methylation with methyl triflate in diethyl ether (Supporting Information). They are easy to purify and benchtop-stable for months. The generated Fischer's base then reacts

with a Vilsmeier intermediate to produce the desired cyanine (Scheme 4B). We optimized the synthesis of the reported 2-ethylidene indolium **20**³³ using bases of different strengths, AcONa, NaH, Et₃N, and diisopropylethylamine (DIPEA), to find DIPEA as the most effective reagent. For 1'-methyl Cy7 **12**, for example, 2-ethylidene indolium **20** was added after the vinyl chloride intermediate was formed, and DIPEA was introduced dropwise to the reaction mixture. This immediately produced a dark blue-green solution indicating the successful formation of the Cy7 derivative. Overall, we prepared 13 new 1'-substituted Cy5 and Cy7 derivatives in good yields using this general procedure (Table 1, Supporting Information). The main advantage of this method is the easy access not only to mono-substituted but also to disubstituted Cy5 and Cy7 with the same or different heterocyclic ends. Only the **16** derivative was prepared by lithiation of **21** with *n*-BuLi and subsequent condensation with the aldehyde **23**. After acidic treatment, **16** was obtained in good yield (Supporting Information).

Absorption and Emission Properties. The parent unsubstituted Cy7 (**10**) features a rigid and planar structure.⁶³ Its efficient and symmetric HOMO-LUMO orbital overlap, localized within the polyene system, is reflected in an absorption spectrum characterized by a narrow band at 740 nm. The presence of a secondary sub-band around 690 nm was attributed to vibronic transitions from the S₀ state to higher vibrational levels of the S₁ excited state.¹⁷ While it has been demonstrated that substituents on the cyanine chain in the 3'- and 4'-positions can influence the positions and shape of absorption maxima,¹³ we show in this work that the effects of 1'-substituents are significantly more pronounced in cyanines functionalized at the 1'-position. The absorption maxima of the prepared cyanines span in the wavelength ranges of approximately 400–700 nm for Cy5 and 400–750 nm for Cy7 derivatives (Figure 3, Table 2), thus, some substituents induced significant hypsochromic shifts. The effects of bulky alkyl groups (**5**, **6**, **14**, and **15**) are much more pronounced than that of the electron-withdrawing cyano group. However, a hypsochromically shifted broader band with a maximum at 620 nm of the monocyano derivative **16** is changed to a narrow band at 704 nm in symmetric dicyano Cy7 derivative **17**, the spectrum of which closely resembles that of unsubstituted Cy7. The spectra of *i*-Pr- and *t*-Bu-substituted Cy5 and Cy7 possess two significant absorption bands of comparable intensity.

Figure 3. Absorption spectra of selected 1'-substituted Cy5 (A: experimental, B: calculated) and Cy7 (C: experimental, D: calculated) derivatives.

Table 2. UV-Vis Absorption and Emission Properties of 1'-Substituted Cyanines

Cyanine	$\lambda^{\text{abs}} / \text{nm}^a$	$\lambda^{\text{abs}}_{\text{calc}} / \text{nm}^b$	$\lambda^{\text{em}} / \text{nm}^a$	$\varepsilon / 10^5^c$	Φ_{F}^d
1	638	585	665	1.96	0.0165 ± 0.0100
2	640	594	671	2.86	0.205 ± 0.007
3	649	608	680	1.56	0.0098 ± 0.0010
4	628	571	679	0.78	0.0077 ± 0.0010
5	374, 652	349, 610	688	0.39	0.001 ± 0.000
6	375, 561	354, 568	679	0.30	0.001 ± 0.000
7	599	545	645	0.69	0.0471 ± 0.002
8	616	569	652	1.14	0.037 ± 0.003
9	610	564	671	1.06	0.007 ± 0.001
10	740	669	769	2.39	0.158 ± 0.021
11	744	671	780	1.58	0.091 ± 0.006
12	748	685	789	1.46	0.013 ± 0.000
13	638	635	790	0.51	0.052 ± 0.009
14	409, 533	382, 568	785	0.59	0.001 ± 0.000
15	433	413	771	0.45	0.001 ± 0.000
16	620	580	744	0.57	0.098 ± 0.014
17	704	641	744	1.50	0.0122 ± 0.0050

^a Absorption (λ^{abs}) and emission (λ^{em}) maxima found in methanol at room temperature (see the Supporting Information for complete spectra). The concentrations were adjusted to have absorbance in the interval of 0.2–1.0. Two main absorption maxima are listed for some derivatives. ^b Calculated absorption maxima ($\lambda^{\text{abs}}_{\text{calc}}$) at the ZINDO/S level of theory. ^c Molar absorption coefficients, $\varepsilon_{\text{max}}/\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in methanol. ^d Fluorescence quantum yield (Φ_{F}) was measured in methanol and obtained as an absolute value using an integrating sphere. The concentrations were adjusted to have an absorbance below 0.15. The excitation wavelength was set at the absorption maxima. Averages of three independent measurements; standard deviation of the mean is given.

Understanding the Absorption Spectra: Substitution Controls both OPR and BLA. The experimental absorption spectra can be understood in terms of structural changes caused by substituents. Using quantum chemistry methods, we optimized the structures at the CAM-B3LYP level (with dielectric continuum) to investigate how substitution affects symmetry breaking in the studied cyanine dyes (Table 2). We focused on two key modifications: variation of the heteroatom X in one of terminal heterocycle and the R¹ substitution at the 1' position.

The R¹ substituents were responsible for three major structural and electronic modifications. First, they induced BLA, the extent of which depended on the electrophilicity of the substituent. Second, they influenced the bond angles at C1', the carbon adjacent to the =C–C= moiety, due to steric effects, thereby introducing local geometric strain. Third, the R¹ groups facilitated OPR of the terminal heterocyclic group along the C1'–C1 axis, which further contributed to BLA, as discussed earlier. The effects of the substituent X (i.e., the end group) were generally smaller. Such structural modifications significantly affect the photophysical properties of the molecules, in accordance with the general principles outlined earlier, and they are reflected in the corresponding absorption spectra. Indeed, the experimental and calculated absorption maxima for the Cy5 and Cy7 derivatives, presented in Figure 3A, showed good agreement. It is worth noting that the calculated spectra

lack vibronic structures, as the theoretical approach incorporates empirical broadening of the absorption wavelengths at the optimized molecular geometry.

Electronic Effects in the 1'-Position. Substitution in the 1'-position with an electron-withdrawing cyano group induced two key geometrical effects. First, the electron-withdrawing nature of the CN group pulls the electron density, leading to BLA along the polymethine chain. For example, the CN-substituted Cy7 (16) displays a distinct alternating bond pattern ($r_{\text{avg}}(\text{single bond}) = 1.412 \text{ \AA}$; $r_{\text{avg}}(\text{double bond}) = 1.377 \text{ \AA}$), in contrast to the nearly uniform bond lengths observed for 10 ($r_{\text{avg}} = 1.391 \text{ \AA}$). Second, the relatively small size of the CN group induces only a modest OPR (15°). Both BLA and OPR contribute to the observed blue shift of the S₀→S₁ absorption band. However, the spectral impact of the 15° OPR is small, as the shift induced by OPR becomes significant only at larger torsional angles (Figure 1). Notably, the spectral shifts due to BLA are more pronounced in the cyano-substituted derivative than in the unsubstituted cyanine, where the same BLA is artificially imposed (Figure S83). This enhancement reflects strong electronic communication between the polymethine backbone and the electron-withdrawing group. Analogous spectral shifts were also observed for the unsubstituted and substituted Cy5s, 1 ($r_{\text{avg}} = 1.392 \text{ \AA}$) and 7 ($r_{\text{avg}}(\text{single bond}) = 1.415 \text{ \AA}$; $r_{\text{avg}}(\text{double bond}) = 1.384 \text{ \AA}$; OPR = 15°), respectively. Interestingly, the hypsochromic shift observed for the mono-CN derivatives

disappears in 1',7'-dicyano derivative **17** as the structure regains its symmetry (Figure 3).

Electronic Effect of the Ending Group (X Substituent). To address the effect of substitution at the X position, we first performed an *in silico* study comparing the unsubstituted **10** and **11** derivatives. Cyanine bearing different terminal heterocycles, 2-methylene-indoline and 2-methylene-2,3-dihydrobenzo[*d*]thiazole, breaks the molecular symmetry and induces BLA along the polymethine chain. The symmetric structure has a bond between the central carbons with $r_{\text{avg}} = 1.391 \text{ \AA}$, while the asymmetric structure exhibits a minor alteration between single ($r_{\text{avg}} = 1.400 \text{ \AA}$) and double bonds ($r_{\text{avg}} = 1.385 \text{ \AA}$). Furthermore, the BLA induced in benzothiazole derivative is rather limited. The geometry-induced spectral changes are compensated by electronic effects, leaving the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ band maximum unchanged (Figure S84). The effect of the X substitution in the terminal heterocycle in Cy5s can also be investigated by comparing the 1'-CN Cy5 **7** ($X = \text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$) with the analogous benzothiazole derivative **8** ($X = \text{S}$). The sulfur substitution induces BLA that compensates for the electrophilicity-driven BLA associated with the cyano group (Figure 3). As a result, **8** exhibits a decrease in BLA ($r_{\text{avg}}(\text{single bond}) = 1.409 \text{ \AA}$; $r_{\text{avg}}(\text{double bond}) = 1.390 \text{ \AA}$), thereby slightly reducing the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ energy gap (Figure 3A). The overall outcome is a rather small change in the spectra, both in theory and in experiment.

Steric Effects in the 1'-Position. Next, we discuss the effect of bulky 1'-substituents (especially, *i*-Pr (**14**) and *t*-Bu (**15**) in Cy7s, where both OPR and BLA effects are pronounced (Figure 3, Table 2). Both structures contain sulfur at the X position, which promotes minor BLA along the polymethine chain. The *i*-propyl group introduces $\text{OPR} = 41^\circ$, whereas the *t*-butyl substituent triggers $\text{OPR} = 79^\circ$. Such high OPR values induce non-negligible BLA, which adds to BLA induced by X substitution, resulting in $r_{\text{avg}}(\text{single bond}) = 1.431 \text{ \AA}$ and $r_{\text{avg}}(\text{double bond}) = 1.367 \text{ \AA}$ for **14** and $r_{\text{avg}}(\text{single bond}) = 1.446 \text{ \AA}$ and $r_{\text{avg}}(\text{double bond}) = 1.359 \text{ \AA}$ for **15**. The combination of both OPR and BLA effects contributes to a significant hypsochromic shift of the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ absorption band. Interestingly, due to an abnormally high OPR, we observed dual absorption bands corresponding to the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ and $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transitions, with the latter transition fully dominating in the 1'-*t*-butyl cyanine (Figure 3).

Finally, we discuss the effects of the benzothiazole group on the structure of Cy5 bearing the same bulky 1'-*i*-Pr substituent. More pronounced BLA and OPR in **6** ($r_{\text{avg}}(\text{single bond}) = 1.426 \text{ \AA}$, $r_{\text{avg}}(\text{double bond}) = 1.374 \text{ \AA}$, $\text{OPR} = 42^\circ$) result in a stronger hypsochromic shift of the first absorption band (Figure 3, Table 2) and alternate more the polymethine chain than observed in indoline derivative **5** ($r_{\text{avg}}(\text{single bond}) = 1.405 \text{ \AA}$, $r_{\text{avg}}(\text{double bond}) = 1.389 \text{ \AA}$, $\text{OPR} = 26^\circ$).

Solvent Effects. Cyanine dyes were shown to exhibit small hypsochromic shifts in their absorption spectra with increasing solvent polarity,⁶⁴⁻⁶⁵ which was interpreted as a consequence of different stabilization of the ground and

excited states of these molecules.⁶⁶ Increasing the polarity of the solvent is also accompanied by a band broadening represented by the growth of the short-wavelength shoulder.^{65, 67} It has been suggested that broad absorption bands in the blue region are related to the broken-symmetry ground state.^{26, 68-69}

Here, we recorded the absorption spectra of several 1'-substituted Cy5 and Cy7 derivatives. The solvent polarity played a significant role in the relative intensity ratio of the two major absorption bands of **5** (Figure 5A), where the band at $\sim 380 \text{ nm}$ and the shoulder in the 500–600 nm region were more pronounced in polar solvents. This would be consistent with the partial charge-transfer character of the second transition, although the intensity change was not found in the calculated data, except for a small difference for **6** between dichloromethane and more polar solvents (Figures S85 and S86). A significant hypsochromic shift and the appearance of a new band at $\sim 550 \text{ nm}$ were observed for **6** when dichloromethane was replaced by solvents with higher polarity (Figure 5B). This shift was also reproduced by calculations. We observed changing vibronic contributions in the first absorption band, indicating different structural changes in the S_1 state in different solvents (Figure S87). Other cyanine derivatives, such as **4**, **15**, **14**, and **16**, also exhibited different absorption spectra in dichloromethane compared to those in more polar solvents (Figures S85 and 86).

Figure 5. The absorption spectra of A) **5** and B) **6** in acetonitrile (MeCN), ethanol (EtOH), dichloromethane (DCM), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), acetone, dimethylformamide (DMF), and methanol (MeOH).

Emission Properties. The unsubstituted Cy7 (**10**) exhibits fluorescence with a quantum yield (Φ_F) of approximately 0.16 in methanol at room temperature. This relatively low value is attributed to efficient nonradiative processes that compete with radiative deactivation of the excited state, with photoisomerization identified as the primary pathway for S_1 state deactivation.⁷⁰ Nevertheless, the quantum yield can be efficiently tuned by conformational constraints.⁷¹

The emission maxima and fluorescence quantum yields for all cyanine derivatives in methanol are listed in Table 2. The emission maxima were not significantly affected by the 1'-substituents as significantly as the absorption maxima. These results are in good agreement with our quantum-chemical calculations (IEF-PCM-TD-CAM-B3LYP/6-31+G**). For example, the calculated emission wavelengths of the **14** and **15** derivatives bearing bulky substituents were 724 and 709 nm, respectively, which do not significantly differ from that of unsubstituted Cy7 ($\lambda_{em} = 702$ nm). Furthermore, the 1'-substituted dyes were significantly less fluorescent than their unsubstituted counterparts, only the cyano derivatives were somewhat more emissive ($\Phi_F < 0.1$).

Table 3. Photophysical Properties of 1'-Substituted Cyanines^a

Cy	$\Phi_{\Delta} / 10^{-3}{}^b$	$\Phi_{dec} / 10^{-7}{}^c$
1	1.9 ± 0.3	3.7 ± 0.1
2	4.0 ± 0.5	14.0 ± 0.6
3	0.39 ± 0.06	4.4 ± 0.7
4	0.55 ± 0.05	12.5 ± 1.0
5	n.d. ^d	6.2 ± 0.6
6	n.d. ^d	56.4 ± 2.6
7	0.48 ± 0.06	2.6 ± 0.4
8	1.32 ± 0.10	0.8 ± 0.1
9	2.1 ± 0.2	3.1 ± 0.6
10	8.9 ± 0.1	31 ± 2
11	18.3 ± 2.1	120.0 ± 16.1
12	2.9 ± 0.4	32 ± 7
13	5.9 ± 0.5	190 ± 30
14	n.d. ^d	102.0 ± 5.4
15	n.d. ^d	n.d. ^d
16	5.2 ± 0.8	7.4 ± 0.3
17	6.3 ± 0.9	0.54 ± 0.10

^a In methanol. The general cyanine structure is shown in Table 2. ^b Quantum yields of the 1O_2 production (Φ_{Δ}) determined relative to that of methylene blue ($\Phi_{\Delta} = 0.49$)⁷² for Cy5 derivatives or **1** ($\Phi_{\Delta} = 8.9 \times 10^{-3}$)¹³ for Cy7 derivatives. ^c Quantum yields of photodecomposition (Φ_{dec}) calculated relative to **1** ($\Phi_{dec} = 3.7 \times 10^{-7}$; see the Supporting Information) and **10** ($\Phi_{dec} = 3.1 \times 10^{-6}$).¹³ Averages of three

independent measurements; standard deviation of the mean is given. ^d Not measured.

Singlet Oxygen Production. Cyanine dyes can be used as singlet oxygen (1O_2) sensitizers in photodynamic therapy (PDT).^{52, 73} Strategies to enhance 1O_2 production from these dyes are well-documented, for example, by incorporating heavy atoms into the dye structure to increase intersystem crossing (ISC).^{14, 73} Here, we determined the quantum yield of singlet oxygen production (Φ_{Δ}) in methanol using diphenylisobenzofuran (DPBF) as a singlet oxygen trap, with unsubstituted Cy7 serving as the reference 1O_2 generator.¹³ Methylene blue ($\Phi_{\Delta} = 0.49$)⁷⁴ was used as a reference 1O_2 generator (Table 3). For 1'-substituted cyanines, the Φ_{Δ} values were comparable to those of the unsubstituted dyes; in general, a lower 1O_2 production was observed for Cy5 derivatives.

(Photo)stability. Photobleaching is a critical factor in the use of fluorophores for biological applications.⁷⁵ Cyanines are known for their photosensitivity,⁷⁶ creating a strong demand for cyanine derivatives with improved stability under irradiation.^{28, 77-78} The photosensitization of 1O_2 is considered to be the primary degradation pathway, leading to dioxetane formation and subsequent cleavage of the polyene chain.¹⁰ In this work, photodecomposition quantum yields (Φ_{dec}) were determined for most derivatives in methanol (Table 3). In general, 1'-functionalized Cy5s showed the same or slightly lower photostability compared to their unsubstituted analogs. A similar trend was found for Cy7 derivatives, with one notable exception, **16**, which had four times lower Φ_{dec} than the unsubstituted Cy7. The synthesized compounds were shown to be stable in the dark in methanol solutions left overnight.

Conclusions

In this work, we present a versatile and efficient synthetic approach for introducing substituents at the C1' chain position of pentamethine and heptamethine cyanines, which offers precise control over their structural and photophysical characteristics. By systematically varying the electronic and steric nature of these substituents, we uncovered two symmetry-breaking mechanisms - bond length alternation (BLA) and out-of-plane rotation (OPR) - that dictate their optical behavior. Our detailed quantum chemical and spectroscopic analyses revealed that OPR acts as an independent driver of BLA, particularly when the chain-end group dihedral angle increases. In this regime, OPR-induced BLA surpasses BLA caused by electronic effects such as substituent electrophilicity, leading to a redistribution of bonding character along the polymethine chain. This deviation from canonical cyanine conjugation explains the observed modulation in absorption properties and electronic transition intensities. Interestingly, the geometric distortion induced by OPR can effectively suppress the electronic influence of C1' substituents, highlighting the delicate balance between steric and electronic contributions to dye behavior.

Substitution at the 1' position allows for tuning of fluorescence intensity, singlet oxygen generation, and photostability – critical parameters for applications in bioimaging, phototherapy, and optoelectronics. For instance, electron-withdrawing cyano groups not only modify the spectral position of the absorption but also impact excited-state lifetimes and resistance to photobleaching. Our findings provide a conceptual framework for designing dyes with enhanced performance and functional specificity. Overall, this study establishes C1' chain substitution as a powerful design handle for engineering cyanine dyes beyond traditional strategies, offering chemical strategies for fluorophore optimization.⁷⁹ The synthetic technique reported here paves the way for the rational development of cyanines with tailored optical properties for various applications.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Materials and methods; synthesis; NMR, absorption and emission spectra; quantum-chemical calculations. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>."

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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TOC Graphics

